

DEVELOPMENT OF DIGITAL LITERARY CONTENT FOR COLLEGE STUDENTS THROUGH H5P

Malaykumar J. Joshi,

Research Scholar Department of Languages (English), Bhakt Kavi Narsinh Mehta University (BKNMU), Junagadh, Gujarat

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Abstract

21st century has begun its march of changes and transformations with support of technology. At a time when almost all the fields are being converted into digital mode, Education also need wide transformation in all over. The classroom generation of the century is keen to technology because of internet. The students seem more interested in anything served through computers and mobile phones. The paper book loses its charm in the era of screen. The education of this century must be supported by technology and the teachers must consider this factor while presenting in the classroom. The learning content can be digitalized and presented in an interactive way so that the modern learner can interestingly deal with it.

The present article aims to introduce a worth web platform which can enrich education in the modern era. The teachers of 21st century are expected to use technology in the classroom for effective and interactive teaching.

INTRODUCTION:

21st century has begun its march of changes and transformations with support of technology. At a time when almost all the fields are being converted into digital mode, Education also need wide transformation in all over. The classroom generation of the century is keen to technology because of internet. The students seem more interested in anything served through computers and mobile phones. The paper book loose its charm in the era of screen. The education of this century must be supported by technology and the teachers must consider this factor while presenting in the classroom. The learning content can be digitalized and presented in an interactive way so that the modern learner can interestingly deal with it.

“Achieving effective learning via digital media continues to be a major concern in contemporary education. The daily use of all forms of digital media is part of our lives and therefore becomes a key component of education.” (Ming-tso, “Jemmy”, Chien, University of Denver, USA) As internet is a major source of information, it must be applied into the classroom teaching. There are so many resources and web-tools which can be great help in developing digital materials for interactive teaching and learning. The present article introduces such a platform which facilitates interactive content development that can be used online anytime, anywhere. The internet based free platform named ‘H5P’ is a resource with variety of content forms.

Key words – Digital content, H5P, Web tools,

WHAT IS DIGITAL CONTENT?

“Digital content is any content that exists in the form of digital data.” (Wikipedia). H5P provides digital content development options for teaching, learning and assessment.

H5P: H5P is a free and open-source content collaboration framework based on JavaScript. H5P is an abbreviation for HTML5 Package, and aims to make it easy for everyone to create, share and reuse interactive HTML5 content. Interactive videos, interactive presentations, quizzes, interactive timelines and more have been developed and shared using H5P on H5P.org. (Wikipedia)

Goals of H5P

- Attract a large worldwide community of skilled people who create, use and share H5P-libraries with each other
- Facilitate worldwide sharing of a large variety of HTML-based content and technologies
- Make it easy for content creators to deliver and publish HTML content on different CMS, LMS, LCMS and other frameworks
- Contribute to better HTML5 content by making it even easier to cooperate and reuse great web technology. (<https://h5p.org/roadmap>)

ROLE OF H5P IN DEVELOPING DIGITAL CONTENT:

So far as digital content is concerned, H5P can play an important role in its creation and sharing with others. A teacher has wide range of selection of content type. One can create...

- Course presentation
- Quiz
- multiple-choice test
- game

- interactive video and audio
- presentations
- Collage
- Flashcards
- Dictation
- Image games
- Timeline
- Virtual tour and more.

At a time when the traditional approaches of teaching, learning and evaluating are being out-dated rapidly, an educator can develop such variety of content and link it with the classroom teaching. The modern students who have more interest in learning by screen and clicks can be entertained as well as encouraged for learning.

REQUIREMENTS FOR USING H5P: H5P can be used with basic requirements of tools and skills. A teacher who has basic command over computer can use H5P and create digital content. The only requirement of tools is a set of computer with internet connection which is easily available nowadays. The developer of the content should keep the content ready to add and attach it to the H5P platforms. One can take help of user manual of the website to learn how to create digital content on H5P. The link of the user manual is <https://h5p.org/content-types-and-applications> .

ADVANTAGES OF H5P DIGITAL CONTENT: There are so many positive feedbacks of the students regarding H5P digital content. Some of the key feedbacks are as under:

- No cost digital content
- Easy to create and use in the classroom
- Makes learning interactive and entertaining
- A big support to the teacher in teaching-learning process
- One time creation can last for life time
- Free platform providing variety of content creation facility
- Facilitates multi-media based interactive content
- Student centred material which can encourage learning
- The digital content can be used anytime, anywhere and any speed

LIMITATIONS OF H5P: Anything digital has some limitations of its use and application. The classrooms where infrastructure is poor with lack of technical tools like internet, computer

and projector, it is difficult to present with H5P content. Some of the major limitations of this platform are as under.

- Cannot be used without internet connection and computer set
- A teacher and students lacking basic computer knowledge cannot use it
- Quite time consuming in creating digital content
- It's a free platform so it may withdraw anytime in future
- Difficult to apply in the hectic schedule of Indian classrooms

These limitations of H5P can be undoubtedly overcome by the enthusiastic teachers who believe in serving interactive content to the students for effective learning.

APPLICATION POSSIBILITIES IN CLASSROOMS: It is always difficult to apply innovative changes in the classrooms where there are numbers of student, a lack of infrastructure and modern teaching aids. Yet, presently almost colleges have at least one computer set with internet and projector. Generally digital content has more effect in person but a teacher can also present it through projector in front of the classroom or the teacher can share link of the H5P content with parents of students which can be learnt at home. The digital content can be more effective than the traditional content presented through paper and blackboards.

CONCLUSION: The present article aims to introduce a worth web platform which can enrich education in the modern era. The teacher of 21st century is expected to use technology in the classroom for effective and interactive teaching. And for that one must peep into the treasure of internet. The web tools are a great help in creating and sharing of interactive content in the classroom. H5P is such a platform which provides a range of digital content creation. Its features can be a good support for effective education. As a teacher of modern students, one must participate in creating and sharing digital content so that the goals of modern education can be achieved.

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